

TREATMENT OF URINARY TRACT INFECTIONS IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 1 DIABETES MELLITUS

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Purpose of the study: to determine the feasibility of including the immunomodulator Imunofan in the treatment of exacerbation of urinary tract infections (UTI) in patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus (DM).

Materials and methods. The study included 125 people: 35 practically healthy people (control group); 30 patients with diabetes without UTI; 30 patients with UTI on the background of type 1 diabetes who received traditional antibacterial and symptomatic therapy, and 30 patients with type 1 diabetes and UTI who received, in addition to traditional therapy, the immunomodulator arginyl-alpha-aspartyl-lysyl-valyl-tyrosyl-arginine (Imunofan) 1 ml intramuscularly 1 time per day for 10 days. A study of the cellular and humoral components of immunity was carried out on the 1st day from the moment of exacerbation of UTI and the start of therapy and after 8 weeks, in the convalescence phase.

Results. The inclusion of Imunofan in basic therapy contributed to the correction of the immunological status: a more significant increase in the concentrations of T-lymphocytes CD3+, CD4+ and the immunoregulatory index (CD4+ /CD8+) was observed, and the levels of CD3+, being within normal values, exceeded those in healthy people. The CD4+ subpopulation continued to increase and after 8 weeks reached the level of that in patients with diabetes without UTI. The HLA-DR content under the influence of Imunofan exceeded the upper limit of the normal range. Treatment with Imunofan also increased the indices of the phagocytic component of innate immunity (phagocytic activity of leukocytes, bactericidal activity of neutrophils in spontaneous and stimulated tests with nitroblue tetrazolium), levels of IgG and IgA and decreased the content of interleukins 4 and 1 β and tumor necrosis factor α .

Conclusion. The study of the dynamics of the state of the cellular and humoral components of innate and adaptive immunity made it possible to establish that in case of UTI against the background of type 1 diabetes, a sluggish inflammatory process is observed with a slowdown in the timing of convalescence. The inclusion of Imunofan in the treatment of UTI corrects the impaired parameters and reduces the risk of progression of chronic kidney disease in UTI against the background of type 1 diabetes.

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